

Computer Vision Syndrome among undergraduate medical students in Jazan University, Saudi Arabia

Turki Mohammed Alqarni^{1*}, Alhanouf Adel Hadi Hakami², Mohammed Qassem Dibaji³

¹General Physician at King Abdulaziz Hospital, Saudi Arabia.

²General Practitioner at Prince Mohammed Bin Nasser hospital, Saudi Arabia.

³Ophthalmology/Glaucoma Specialist (at Prince Mohammed Bin Nasser hospital), Saudi Arabia.

*Email: Turki.mohd17@gmail.com

Abstract

Background:

Computer vision syndrome (CVS) is “a complex of eye and vision problems related to near work experienced during computer use.” The usage of electronic devices is significantly essential for students as a method of studying. Computer vision syndrome It is one of the rising health concerns related to technology (cell phones and tablets) due to continuous use of computers among students. Symptoms of CVS include dry and irritated eyes, eye strain/fatigue, blurred vision, red eyes, burning eyes, excessive tearing, double vision, headache, light/glare sensitivity, slowness in changing focus, and changes in color perception. The mechanism of CVS is a result of people blinking less than usual when concentrating for a long period on visual tasks. This behavior dries up the ocular surface, and along with the prolonged use of the ciliary muscle, the eyes get irritated. Fortunately, CVS does not have any long-term or serious complications since it is only an eye symptom and not a disease. Simply allowing the eyes to focus on a distant object or wearing specific glasses for reading will reduce eye strain. **Aim:** this study aimed to estimate the prevalence and to assess the risk factors as well as the knowledge about computer vision syndrome among undergraduate medical students. **Method:** A cross-sectional study conducted in Jazan University, Jazan, Saudi Arabia from June 2020 to September 2020. 150 undergraduate medical students from the second to the sixth year were enrolled in the study by nonprobability convenience sampling. An electronic survey adapted from previous literature research on Computer Vision Syndrome used for data collection. **Result:** A total of 150 participants were invited to participate in the study: 92.67 % (139) of the participants using a computer, tablets or smartphones

for studying were included. 11 (7.33%) participants were excluded from the study as they reported that they did not use computers while they are studying. Logistic regression was conducted to assess whether the predictor variables were significantly associated with CVS in the students. Logistic regression analyzes these variables if significantly predicted whether or not a student with computer vision syndrome. When all four predictor variables are considered together, they significantly predict computer vision syndrome among students, ($\chi^2= 14.55$, $df= 6$, $N=139$, $p =0.024$. which is < 0.05 . **Conclusion:** Studying from electronic methods led to an increased incidence of CVS, and students using electronic methods had a higher chance of developing CVS. Computer vision syndrome is common among medical students; significant risk factors need to be addressed to reduce the symptom and to ensure a better productivity of work. It is a necessity to raise awareness among medical students regarding computer-related health problems.

Key words: Computer, Vision Syndrome, undergraduate, medical, students, Jazan, University, Saudi Arabia

1.1 Introduction:

The American Optometric Association describes the Computer Vision Syndrome (CVS) as a group of eye and vision problems related to events that stress near vision and are experienced in relation to or during computer use. CVS related eye and vision symptoms occur due to prolonged computers, tablets, e-readers, and cell phone use.[1] Nowadays, the use of computers has become universal. In our personal, professional, and educational lives, computer technology plays an integral role with the growing use of computers by a young adult in educational institutions as well as at home, there is a need to investigate the students if they follow the ergonomic concepts and principles while using the computers. [2]

CVS symptoms occur due to an ocular etiology that caused by abnormalities in the ocular surface or accommodating spasms as well as extra-ocular (ergonomic) etiologies. Symptoms of CVS include; eye strain, fatigue, dry eye, irritated eyes, blurred vision, burning eyes, red eyes, double vision, excessive tear secretion, light or glare sensitivity, contact lens discomfort, changes in color perception, headache, slowness in changing focus, and neck, shoulder, and backache. [3] Video Display Terminal VDT is known as a computer screen. It has also shown that VDT users also have a higher incidence of complaints than non-VDT users in the same environment.[4] One or more factors may be responsible for the development of CVS. These

factors are uncomfortable sitting position, infrequent blinking, prolonged continues looking at the digital screens, improper lightening conditions, glare, am tropic, and incorrect distances between the eye and the computer. [3]

CVS is growing public health problem and contributing significantly towards reducing the quality of life and productivity at the workplace, according to American optometric association nearly report, 14% of patients report for ocular examination because of computer vision syndrome and such effected individuals are not even aware that they are suffering from this condition.[5] It is estimated that approximately 60 million people suffer from CVS globally and that a million new cases occur each year. [6,7]

The Prevalence of CVS among office workers and the students in different countries around the world is as follows: Sri-Lanka (67.4%),[6] India (80.3%)[8], and United Arab Emirates (UAE) (72%). [9] In Saudi Arabia, studies were conducted in two cities on mobile phone users and students. The Prevalence is those two cities are: Jeddah (97.3%) [10], and Al-Ahasa 43.5% [11]

Many studies showed an increase in the Prevalence of CVS among office workers and college students.[3,6,7,10] Moreover, due to the COVID-19 pandemic issue and accompanying quarantine in 2020, many academic institutions, such as universities, shifted to online classes and exams. Furthermore, students during this pandemic are sitting at home most of the time. They would be increasing the duration of using their computers to study, attending lectures, doing assignments, and examinations. Mostly they will spend more than the usual time online. For those reasons, we expect to find a high CVS incidence among students at this time. Up to date, there is a lack of studies that assess the Prevalence and level of awareness of CVS in the southern part of Saudi Arabia, so we aim to determine the Prevalence, identify the risk factors and to evaluate the knowledge of CVS among undergraduate medical students in Jazan University.

1.2- Rationale:

- Nowadays, the use of computers has become universal. In our personal, professional, and educational lives, computer technology plays an integral role with the growing use of computers by a young adult in educational institutions what resulted for computer

Vision Syndrome (CVS) is a widespread as a group of eye and vision problems related to events that stress near vision and are experienced in relation to or during computer use. CVS related eye and vision symptoms occur due to prolonged computers, tablets, e-readers, and cell phone use many undergraduate medical students have misunderstood the used of prolonged computers, tablets, e-readers, and cell phone.

- To the knowledge of the researcher no similar study had been conducted in medical students in Jazan University.

1.3- Aim:

To estimate the prevalence and to assess the risk factors as well as the knowledge about computer vision syndrome among undergraduate medical students.

1.4- Objectives:

- To estimate the prevalence and to assess the risk factors as well as the knowledge about computer vision syndrome among undergraduate medical students.
- To determine association between Risk Factor and computer vision syndrome

2- Literature review

To the best of our knowledge, there are no published studies assessing the Computer Vision Syndrome among undergraduate medical students in Jazan University in Saudi Arabia. American Optometric Association has proposed a few practices that can help tallness the mindfulness about Computer Vision Syndrome among students. Government of Saudi Arabia has been making a significant effort to ensure that of Computer Vision Syndrome not affecting undergraduate medical students .

Study by Hassan et al. who reported a prevalence of 90.5% among medical students in Pakistan[12]. This is in agreement with a study by Noreen et al.[5], who reported a prevalence of 77.4% among medical students in Pakistan. also Reddy et al. provided a prevalence of 89.9% among university students in Malaysia [13].

However, a lower prevalence was observed in other studies among engineering and medical students (67.2% and 77.4%, respectively)[5,14] . Noteworthy in regard to gender, females were observed to have more risk of CVS. &is association agrees with the findings by Guillon and Ma"issa who studied the effect of gender on tear film evaporation, which showed a significant

high evaporation rate in females, thus higher risk of CVS[15], in addition, Straker et al. studied the association between gender and posture during computer use, which concluded that females had greater prevalence of neck/shoulder pain [16].

Other studies in Sri Lanka, India, and United Arab Emirates also support the significantly high CVS prevalence among female computer workers, with significantly higher headache and blurred vision incidence[17,6,9] . Students in this study were relatively young, with a mean age of 21.65 years. No significant associations were found between the year of medical school and the age with CVS. However, Ranasinghe et al. found a significantly higher prevalence of CVS among those aged more than 40 years compared with those aged less than 20 years [6].

Guillon and Maïssa also noted a significantly higher tear film evaporating rate in patients older than 45 years compared with younger individuals, which exaggerate symptoms of dryness associated with CVS[15]. Refractive errors including myopia and hyperopia showed no significant association with CVS. However, astigmatism was associated significantly with CVS symptoms. Previous experimental studies showed a significant increase in symptoms in individuals with uncorrected residual astigmatism[18,19] .

If refractive errors are uncorrected including myopia, hyperopia, and astigmatism, they contribute to the symptoms of CVS [1]. Results were contradicted by Ranasinghe et al. who found a significantly higher CVS among contact lens wearers; furthermore, contact lens wearers are more prone to dryness which exacerbate CVS symptoms[6,20] . While Reddy et al. found university students who wear spectacles had significantly more CVS symptoms than those who do not wear spectacles during computer use[13] .

Furthermore, a study in Chennai revealed a significantly higher risk of developing headache and blurred vision among students wearing corrective lens, including both spectacles and contact lens [17].

This study matched several other investigations that have cited dry eye as a major contributor to CVS among participants using electronic devices[21] . However, the results disagreed with Chu et al. [20], who did not observe significant differences in dry eye symptoms

between the hard copy and computer conditions. Due to the limited sample size, the results should be interpreted with caution.

Methodology.

3.1: Study Design:

A cross-sectional study conducted in Jazan University, Jazan, Saudi Arabia from June 2020 to September 2020. Aims to assess the prevalence of Computer Vision Syndrome among undergraduate medical students, risk factors, and preventive habits (Ergonomic practice).

3.2: Study Area:

This study has been conducted in Jazan University, Jazan city, which is located in Saudi Arabia. An electronic survey adapted from previous literature research on Computer Vision Syndrome used for data collection.[1] One hundred fifty undergraduate medical students from the second to the sixth year were enrolled in the study by nonprobability convenience sampling.

3.3. Study Population:

This study has been conducted in Jazan University, constituted the study population undergraduate medical students from the second to the sixth year were enrolled in the study by nonprobability convenience sampling. The total number of 150 students. An electronic survey adapted from previous literature research on Computer Vision Syndrome used for data collection. [1]

3.4 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

3.4.1 Inclusion Criteria

Undergraduate medical students who use their laptops or tablets while studying.

3.4.2 Exclusion Criteria

Medical students who not agree to participate in our study before participation

3.5 Sample size:

The sample size for this study was calculated. Descriptive data were presented as percentages. Unadjusted odds ratios (OR) to measure the association's strength, 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated. A Chi-square test used to lend statistical support to prove associations between categorical variables.

3.6 Sampling technique:

The researcher has been using simple random sample technique. The researcher obtained the approval from through personal communication before using the questionnaire form, after that, The researcher has been Permission from the regional Research and Ethical Committee and participants. The online survey will be disabled when the sample size is achieved, the primary participants will be requested to rollout the survey further, the study has been conducted in Jazan University One hundred fifty undergraduate medical students from the second to the sixth year in the study .

3.7 Data collection tool:

The survey included demographic data, studying habits when using Computer (Regarded as risk factors): duration of studying using computers, take breaks and duration of breaks during studying, distance and Level from laptop/tablet screen, seating posture, source of lightning, Brightness of laptop/tablet screen and using a filter and antiglare screen. Moreover, the questionnaire includes the frequency of ocular and extra ocular symptoms of Computer Vision Syndrome .

The study questionnaire has been validated by three consultants and statistically tested after two Arabic Language teachers checked it for Linguistics and spelling accuracy.

3.8 Study field :

Study has been conducted take place between June 2020 to September 2020.

.39 Data Collection Technique:

A total of 150 undergraduate medical students from the second to the sixth year were enrolled in the study by nonprobability convenience sampling.

Interviews were conducted using the self-structured questionnaire. Interviews with undergraduate medical students from the second to the sixth year were enrolled in the study by nonprobability convenience sampling, Ocular symptoms include burning sensation, dry eye, red eye, blurred vision, sensation of foreign body, increased sensitivity to light, ocular pain, excessive tearing and itching, double vision, and change in color visualization. Extra ocular symptoms include headache, neck, shoulder or back pain, and numbness of the hand and fingers. Furthermore, the questionnaire includes preventive measures (Ergonomic practice) and

habits taken to reduce the symptoms, in Jazan University, Jazan, Saudi Arabia from June 2020 to September 2020.

On the other hand, control subjects were interviewed during the whole week from Sunday to Thursday. By the end of the interviews, the researcher presented thanks, advice and appreciation

3.10 A Pilot study

Was carried out at the questions were first pre-tested and were revised and finalized after it was pilot tested. Before completing the survey, participants were required to indicate their consent using a forced response question followed by the survey questionnaires. This study has been conducted and all suggestions taken into consideration.

3.11 Data analyzed

Descriptive data were presented as percentages. Unadjusted odds ratios (OR) to measure the association's strength, 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated. A Chi-square test used to lend statistical support to prove associations between categorical variables. A correlation analysis (Kendall) was done between computer use and associated risk factors. Kendall correlation coefficient and corresponding P values were estimated. P-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant, using (SPSS version 25).

3.12 Ethical consideration :

- Permission from family medicine program was obtained .
- Permission from the regional Research and Ethical Committee has been given to conduct our study.
- All the subjects have been participating voluntarily in the study .
- Privacy of information and confidentiality has been maintained .
- Full explanation about the study and its purpose was carried out to obtain their participation.

3.13 Budget: Self-funded

4. Result:

A total of 150 participants were invited to participate in the study: 92.67 % (139) of the participants using a computer, tablets or smartphones for studying were included. 11 (7.33%) participants were excluded from the study as they reported that they did not use computers while they are studying. 67.6% (94) of the included participants were females and 32.4% (45) were males. Age ranged between 19 and 27 years, with a mean of (22.06±1.71) years. Frequency of Computer Vision Syndrome experienced on continuous computer work calculated. High prevalence of CVS was observed, in which 92.8% (129) of students reported at least one symptom of CVS during studying using computers. (**Table 1**)

Table 1: presence of symptom CVS during studying using computers

CVS		
	N	%
Negative	10	7.2
Positive	129	92.8
Total	139	100.0

Association between gender and computer vision syndrome

The percentage of CVS among female was 93.6% (88) while in male 91.1% (41) with no significant association was found between the CVS and gender since result showed poor Kendall's r and odd ratios. P values greater than 0.05.

(Table 2).

Table 2: Association between gender and computer vision syndrome

		CVS Negative	CVS positive	OR	P value	95% CI Lower Bound upper Bound		Kendall's r
Gender	Male	4	41	1.431	.594	.383	5.347	0.045
	Female	6	88					
Total		10	129					

Reference categories: CVS is Negative and gender is male.

Interpretation of above table: An odds ratio = (1.461) > 1, indicates that the likelihood of computer vision syndrome occurring is more likely for the response category (Females) than the referent category (Males) of an independent variable (Gender). P= 0.594.

Frequency of CVS symptoms experienced on computer work

The most experienced symptoms frequently were neck, shoulder, or back pain 79.9% (111), headache 77.7% (108), followed by eye pain 56.8% (79), and itching 56.1% (78) (**Figure 1 and 2**). The least experienced symptoms were heavy eyelids 32.4% (45), colored halos around the objects 33.1% (46), feeling that sight is worsening 34.5% (48). (**Table 3**)

Figure 1: Frequency of ocular symptoms of computer vision syndrome. Eye pain was the most commonly reported symptom.

Figure 2: Frequency of Extraocular symptoms of computer vision syndrome. Neck, shoulder or back pain was the most commonly reported symptom.

Table 3: frequency of CVS symptoms experienced on computer work

Symptoms	Negative CVS		Positive CVS	
	N	%	N	%
Burning	63	45.3	76	54.7
Itching	61	43.9	78	56.1
Feeling of foreign body	73	52.5	66	47.5
Tearing	62	44.6	77	55.4
Excessive blinking	83	59.7	56	40.3
Eye redness	66	47.5	73	52.5
Eye pain	60	43.2	79	56.8
Heavy eyelids	94	67.6	45	32.4
Dryness	71	51.1	68	48.9
Blurred vision	80	57.6	59	42.4
Double vision	111	79.9	28	20.1
Difficulty focusing for near vision	76	54.7	63	45.3
Increased sensitivity to light	70	50.4	69	49.6
Colored halos around objects	93	66.9	46	33.1
Feeling that sight is worsening	91	65.5	48	34.5
Headache	31	22.3	108	77.7
Neck, shoulder or back pain	28	20.1	111	79.9
Numbness of hands/fingers	70	50.4	69	49.6

Association between Risk Factor and computer vision syndrome:

Regarding risk factors, three of nine variables (study hours duration using laptop/tablet per day, posture style, and Source of lightening) associated significantly with computer vision syndrome. Other variables showed poor Kendall's r and chi-square. P-values > 0.05. (Table 4)

(Table 4): Association between Risk Factor and computer vision syndrome.

Risk Factor	Classes	CVS Negative	CVS positive	Chi-Square	P value	95% CI		Kendall's r
						Lower Bound	upper Bound	
1. study duration using laptop/tablet per day:	1-2 hours	2	11	4.318	.047*	0.044	0.055	0.171*
	3-4 hours	4	26					
	>4 hours	4	92					
2. take breaks	Yes	10	118	.926	.336	0.593	0.618	0.082
	No	0	11					
3. break duration after	No	0	11	2.852	.429	0.416	0.442	0.06
	<30 minutes	3	37					
	30-60 minutes	6	49					
	>60 minutes	1	32					

4.Distance from screen:	>Arm & Forearm length	4	33	.988	.320	0.441	0.467	0.084
	<Arm & Forearm length	6	96					
5.posture style	Sitting	7	41	6.046	.049*	0.044	0.055	.198*
	Lying	0	3					
	Both	3	85					
6.Level of the screen:	Below level of the eyes	4	84	3.420	.156	0.147	0.166	0.122
	Same level of the eyes	6	41					
	Above level of the eyes	0	4					
7.Source of lightening	From the ceiling/wall	5	102	10.198	.029*	0.024	0.033	-0.166-*
	Natural light (windows)	1	9					
	Table lamp	4	11					
	In the dark	0	7					
8.Brightness of screen:	Very bright	1	2	4.248	.294	0.283	0.306	0.093
	Bright	5	61					
	Dull	4	51					
	Dark	0	15					
9.using screen filter/anti-glare	Yes	4	31	1.256	0.262	0.435	0.460	0.095
	No	6	98					

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Logistic regression analysis to assess the risk of different variables in the incidence of CVS

Logistic regression was conducted to assess whether the predictor variables were significantly associated with CVS in the students. Refractive errors including (myopia, hyperopia, astigmatism), wearing eyeglasses, wearing contact lenses, history of refractive error surgery, chronic diseases, and history of medications that can cause eye symptoms and ocular side effects including (antidepressants, antiepileptic, anticoagulant, antituberculosis, Roaccutane).

Logistic regression analyzes these variables if significantly predicted whether or not a student with computer vision syndrome. When all four predictor variables are considered together, they significantly predict computer vision syndrome among students, ($\chi^2= 14.55$, $df= 6$, $N=139$, $p =0.024$. which is < 0.05).

Logistic regression Predicting computer vision syndrome presents the odds ratios that suggest that the odds of 7.1% estimate computer vision syndrome if the student is known to have refractive errors. (Table 5)

Myopia, hyperopia, and astigmatism were statistically significant associated with CVS ($P < 0.05$). There is no significant association between the students who wear eyeglasses or contact lenses when studying and CVS. Also. No association between CVS and participants with a history of medication, chronic diseases, refractive error, and eye surgeries (P -value > 0.05).

		B	S.E.	P	Odd ratio
Step 1 ^a	Refractive errors	-2.652-	1.103	.016*	.071
	wear eyeglasses	-.420-	.792	.596	.657
	wear contact lens	17.947	8338.381	.998	62299240.182
	eye surgeries	-.514-	1.212	.672	.598
	Hypertension	18.245	20558.946	.999	83915674.108
	Diabetes	B	0	0	0
	Medications that affects your vision	18.038	16694.686	.999	68169556.994
	Constant	4.337	1.114	.000	76.481

b. Estimation terminated at iteration number 5 because parameter estimates changed by less than .001.

Frequency of Preventive measures among the participants

The most applied preventive habits (Ergonomic practices) were using ceiling light (overhead light) other than the light hitting directly on the eyes 62.60%, avoiding direct blow of air on eyes 59.7%, while the least ergonomic practices were trying to use eye lubricants 39.6% and using antiglare filters 33.8%. (Figure 3)

5. Discussion:

High prevalence and lack of awareness about CVS syndrome are considered widespread issue worldwide in the 21st century. In 2020 most of the students use electronic devices while studying; in addition to that, most universities have shifted to online courses and lectures. Our research study aims to assess the prevalence of CVS syndrome and the most common risk factors associated with the medical students at Jazan University, Jazan, Saudi Arabia. Also, to evaluate the frequency of those students who are applying ergonomic practices and preventive measures to minimize the incidence of CVS. Heterogeneity and variation in previous studies

about CVS have shown, which can be related to the varying research methodologies. Among 139 participants enrolled in the study, 92.8% (129) reported at least one symptom. Our study result showed a high prevalence of CVS syndrome compared to previous studies related to medical and university students in Pakistan and Malaysia (90.5% and 89.9%, respectively).[12,13]. Also, our study prevalence is high in accordance to previous studies that found a prevalence of 80.3% among medical and engineering university students in the Indian city of Chennai, 67.4% in Sri-Lanka among computer office workers, 72% among computer using university students in the United Arab Emirates (UAE). [6,,8,9]. Regarding gender and CVS, although the presence of a significant association between female gender and CVS in the previous study.[10] However, our study analysis showed no significant association between gender and CVS (P-value = 0.594) (**Table 2**) which agrees with the results of Doctor Ranganatha S[22]. The most common reported symptom in our study was neck, shoulder, or back pain 79.9% (111), followed by headache 77.7% (108). Likewise, to our study result, Abudawood et al and Ranganatha et al found back, shoulder, or neck pain and headache greatly associated with CVS.[23,22] Furthermore, Al Subaie et al and logaraj et al reported a high frequency of back, shoulder, or neck pain[11,8]. Headache associated with CVS in most of the previous studies. [2,10,9,12,13] . Regarding the risk factors, study hours duration using a laptop/tablet is significantly associated with computer vision syndrome. The longer duration using a computer, the more prevalent CVS symptoms. In addition to that, it is consistent with the findings of many previous studies. [6,23,12,13] Moreover, Noreen et al. and Logaraj et al., among the CVS-positive group, reported a significant association between the students who were spent more than four hours compared to those who spent less than four hours. [5,8] Also, Noreen K observed a correlation between extended duration using a computer and the longer the symptoms last even after work.[5]. A significant association observed between CVS and myopia, hyperopia, and astigmatism. In accordance to AOA, Uncorrected or under-corrected problems of the vision can be a significant contributing risk factor to CVS symptoms. Uncorrected refractive errors like hyperopia, astigmatism, and presbyopia can lead to the incidence of CVS symptoms while working on the computer or any other electronic devices.

[1] Bogdănici et al conducted study to assess the quality of eyesight and computer vision syndrome, study found myopic astigmatism and myopia were the most frequent types of ametropia related to the CVS among the participants. [24]. In regard to students who wear eyeglasses and prescribed contact lenses, there was no significant association noted with CVS. These findings were contradicted with two studies conducted; they found a significantly higher CVS in contact lens wearers; besides that, contact lens wearers are at higher risk of dryness, which aggravates CVS symptoms.[6,20] Abodawood et al conducted study among medical students, study found no significant association between CVS and using of spectacle and contact lenses during studying.[23]. Posture style and source of lightening in our study are significantly associated with CVS. These findings agree with the instruction and guidelines of the American Optometric Association. AOA recommends avoiding using light that hitting directly on the eyes. Moreover, Chairs should be compatible and comfortable padded, and it should also be conforming to the body [1]. Taking breaks frequently not associated significantly with the incidence of CVS. Previous studies correspondingly support the same findings.[6,5,23] In contrast, other studies emphasize the association between frequency of taking breaks and decreasing CVS symptoms.[9,12,8]. Regarding the distance from the screen, we found no significant association between the distance from the screen and CVS. Our findings were compatible with the results of computer workers in the Sri-Lanka. Nevertheless, other studies indicate the association between short distance from the screen and CVS.[9,12] These findings possibly related to inaccurate measurements of the participants. The majority of participants were practicing a good studying habit by keeping the computer screen below the eyes' level, adjusting the screen's level not observed to be associated with the CVS in our study. Locating the screen 10–20° below the eye level of users is recommended. Higher gaze angles will expose more conjunctiva and cornea area, leading to increased tear evaporation rate and, subsequently, more ocular surface-related symptoms. [6,25,20] Supporting the fact, Reddy et al. noted a significant reduction in CVS incidence when the screen adjusted below the eye level. [13]. Antiglare screen or filter to minimize the brightness only a minority of students apply it. No association was observed with CVS and antiglare in our study. Similarly, a

previous study performed and showed no significant association. [23,13]. While evaluating preventive habits, a poor ergonomic practice noted among the major of participants. The participants were poorly applying the rule of 20-20-20. Most of the participants didn't hear about the 20-20-20 rule previously. **(Figure 3)**. Poor ergonomic practices were observed among the students who participate in our study. The pie chart in **(Figure 3)** Summarized preventive habits as percentages. Limitations of our study as following it is a cross-sectional study design conducted in a single university and diagnosis of CVS done according to self-reported symptoms of participants without ophthalmic examination.

6. Conclusion:

Computer vision syndrome is highly frequent among undergraduate medical students who use electronic devices. Shoulder, neck, and back pain, headache, are the most common reported symptoms. Our study shows a significant association among CVS-positive students with study hour's duration using computers per day, posture style, and lightening source. Uncorrected vision and dry eyes were found to be associated with CVS in our study. On the other hand, no association was found between gender and Computer Vision Syndrome. Also, most of the students are not applying preventive habits and ergonomic practices. Therefore, we recommend more efforts and further education to improve the students' knowledge about risk factors, preventative measures, and behaviors to raise their awareness.

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